

ISic1438

I.Sicily inscription 1438

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330085

1. Θεσαλῶ ²⁶Θεσσαλοῦ²⁶ τόδε σᾶμα τῶ [δεῖνα]
2. *huiō*.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644981

EDCS 64800234

PHI 330085

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 26.1094

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à

l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 26 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1975. Koiné alfabetica fra Siracusa, Megara Iblea e Selinunte?. *Kokalos*. 21: 121-153. At 150 no.15 fig.33.2

Arena, R. 1996. Iscrizioni Greche Archaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. Iscrizioni di Sicilia. I. Iscrizioni di Megara Iblea e Selinunte. Pisa. At no.9 tav.4.1

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